

Exciton Fine Structure in 2D Perovskites: The Out-of-Plane Excitonic State

Katarzyna Posmyk, Mateusz Dyksik, Alessandro Surrente, Duncan K. Maude, Natalia Zawadzka, Adam Babiński, Maciej R. Molas, Watcharaphol Paritmongkol, Mirosław Mączka, William A. Tisdale, Paulina Plochocka,* and Michał Baranowski*

2D Ruddlesden-Popper metal-halide perovskites feature particularly strong excitonic effects, making them a fascinating playground for studying exciton physics. A complete understanding of the properties of this quasi-particle is crucial to fully exploit the tremendous potential of 2D perovskites (2DP) in light emission applications. Despite intense investigations, some of the exciton properties remain elusive to date, for example, the energy-ordering of the exciton states within the so-called fine structure manifold. Using optical spectroscopy, it demonstrates that in the archetypical 2DP (PEA)₂PbI₄, in contradiction to theoretical predictions, the energy of the bright out-of-plane exciton state is higher than that of two in-plane states. Having elucidated the order of exciton fine structure, it determines the *g*-factor of the dark exciton transition, together with the values of the electron and hole *g*-factors in the direction parallel to the *c*-axis of the crystal. In this way, it provides for the first time, a complete picture of the exciton fine structure in (PEA)₂PbI₄ 2DP.

dielectric confinement enhance the binding energy of the electron-hole pair to values as large as hundreds of meV.^[1–3] A prominent example is the 2D Ruddlesden-Popper metal-halide perovskites (2DP), in which exciton binding energies reach a few hundred milli-electronvolts.^[1,4–6] Additionally, the soft, polar, and low symmetry lattice of metal-halide perovskites creates a unique background for electron-hole interaction^[1,2,7–11] providing a fascinating playground for studying the exciton properties, which challenges our understanding so far. For instance, the fine structure of exciton states in bulk,^[12–14] nanocrystals^[15–20] and 2D form of perovskites^[21–26] (crucial for light emission applications), despite being intensively investigated, is still a subject of the ongoing debate concerning the order of

these states and how they are affected by quantum confinement.^[12,15,19,20,24,27–30]

In metal halide perovskites, the exchange interaction between the electron and hole spins, together with the crystal field, lifts the degeneracy of the excitonic states. Depending on the crystal symmetry, a partial or complete lifting of the exciton states degeneracy with respect to angular momentum is expected.^[17,28,31–34] Symmetry analysis of the perovskite band structure leads to four

1. Introduction

Optical properties of low-dimensional semiconductor nanostructures are often driven by excitons – a quasi-particle composed of a photo-created electron and hole bound by the Coulomb attraction. Excitonic effects are particularly strong in 2D van der Waals semiconductors, in which simultaneous quantum and

K. Posmyk, M. Dyksik, A. Surrente, P. Plochocka, M. Baranowski
Department of Experimental Physics
Faculty of Fundamental Problems of Technology
Wrocław University of Science and Technology
Wrocław 50-370, Poland
E-mail: paulina.plochocka@lnmci.cnrs.fr;
michal.baranowski@pwr.edu.pl

K. Posmyk, D. K. Maude, P. Plochocka
Laboratoire National des Champs Magnétiques Intenses, UPR 3228
CNRS-UGA-UPS-INSA
Grenoble and Toulouse 38042, France
N. Zawadzka, A. Babiński, M. R. Molas
Institute of Experimental Physics, Faculty of Physics
University of Warsaw
Warsaw 02-093, Poland
W. Paritmongkol, W. A. Tisdale
Department of Chemical Engineering
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, United States
W. Paritmongkol
Department of Chemistry
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, United States
M. Mączka
Institute of Low Temperature and Structure Research
Polish Academy of Sciences
ul. Okólna 2, Wrocław 50-422, Poland

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/adom.202300877>

© 2023 The Authors. Advanced Optical Materials published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/adom.202300877

Figure 1. a) Ladder of exciton fine structure states expected for (PEA)₂PbI₄ showing the possible positions of the Z-state (indicated by dashed lines). b) Scheme of (PEA)₂PbI₄ crystal structure.^[43] c) Scheme of the “plane” and d) “edge” configurations used in our reflectance measurements.

possible exciton states;^[17,31,33] one optically inactive i.e., dark state, which we refer to as *D*, and three optically active bright states (see **Figure 1a**). In the case of 2D materials, symmetry is naturally broken in the *Z* direction (out-of-plane), which splits off the state with the dipole moment oriented along the *c*-axis. We will refer to this state as the *Z* state. Furthermore, if the in-plane symmetry of the crystal is broken, the degeneracy between the two remaining bright states is lifted. In this case, the *X* and *Y* states with dipole moments oriented in the plane of the crystal couple to linearly polarized light, and can be observed in the optical spectra.^[21,22,26] The large exciton binding energy in 2DP results in a particularly strong exchange interaction, and leads to a significant splitting of excitonic states reaching values of a few tens of meV between the dark singlet and the bright triplet states,^[22–24,35,36] and few meV between the in-plane bright triplet states.^[21,22,26] However, even despite the large splitting within the exciton manifold in 2DP, the order of the exciton states remains controversial.^[27,29,31] In particular, the position of the *Z* state^[27] as shown schematically in **Figure 1a** is unclear. Initial theoretical works, based on the multiband effective mass models, together with some experiments, suggested that the exciton state with the out-of-plane dipole moment is the lowest energy state of the bright triplet.^[31,37–39] More recent theoretical studies indicate however that this order might be reversed,^[27] and strongly depends on the quantum confinement.^[24,29] A trace of the *Z*-state above two in-plane states was recently reported in the high magnetic field measurements in the Voigt configuration.^[23] However, its energy at zero magnetic field remains to be elucidated. An experimental determination of the order of the bright exciton states is therefore essential to understand the exciton fine structure, which is crucial for light emission applications and advanced quantum devices.^[19,40,41] The detailed quantification of exciton fine structure will also provide a benchmark for band structure modeling, which remains challenging in metal-halide perovskites.^[42]

Here, we address the problem of the bright exciton fine structure in archetypal 2DP (PEA)₂PbI₄. We demonstrate that the exciton with the out-of-plane dipole moment is the highest energy state within the exciton manifold. Our findings challenge the predictions of the effective mass theory while corroborating very recent ab-initio calculations,^[27] and magneto-optical studies.^[23] The presented results provide a firm base for further studies of the evolution of exciton fine structure splitting with quantum confinement. Moreover, our understanding of the detailed bright exciton fine structure, allows us to determine the previously unknown values of the dark and *Z* exciton *g*-factors along the *c*-axis, and therefore the individual *g*-factors of the electrons and holes.

2. Results and Discussion

We have investigated (PEA)₂PbI₄, with the crystal structure shown in **Figure 1b** (the optical images of an investigated crystal can be found in SI.). It consists of inorganic PbI₄ octahedral units slabs separated by phenylethylammonium chains. The planes of the metal-halide octahedra form a quantum well for carriers, while the organic spacers provide quantum and dielectric confinement. We have examined high-quality single crystals grown by two different methods, to exclude any potential influence of the sample quality on the results. The first crystal was grown using a cooling-induced crystallization method^[44,45] and the second one was prepared by slow evaporation of a solvent at room temperature^[22] (see methods). Our results are both qualitatively and quantitatively the same for both types of crystals. The results presented here correspond to the crystal grown by the first method. The result for the crystal grown by the second method can be found in the Supporting Information (Figures S5–S7, Supporting Information).

For (PEA)₂PbI₄ a complete lifting of the degeneracy of the exciton states with respect to the angular momentum is expected,^[21,22,26] as shown in **Figure 2a**. Each of the bright states

Figure 2. a) Red and green curves representing the reflectance of spectra measured in the “plane” configuration, with the use of two orthogonal linear polarization of reflected light. The blue curve is the reflectance spectrum measured in the “edge” configuration with the polarization along the out-of-plane direction. The scheme indicates the orientation of the particular exciton dipole moments with respect to the sample. Inset; negative derivative of the reflectance spectrum for the “edge” configuration with polarization oriented perpendicular to the sample plane. b) Dependence of the negative derivative of the reflectance spectrum in the “edge” configuration versus polarization angle. Polarization dependence of spectra in the “plane” configuration can be found in S1, similar data have been also presented in the Ref. [22]. c) Polar plot of the intensity of the Z state extracted from the negative derivative of the reflectance spectrum. $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystal structure is shown to provide a reference for the dipole moment orientation. All measurements were done at $T = 4.2$ K.

couples selectively to linearly polarized light along the X, Y, or Z directions. Therefore, the simple combination of appropriate sample orientation and polarization-resolved measurements provides direct access to each of the bright exciton states. Here, we have employed polarization-resolved micro-reflectance measurements at $T = 4.2$ K. Samples were mounted on copper plates in two configurations: “plane” (Figure 1c), where the light was reflected from the crystal plane parallel to the planes of the inorganic sheets. In that configuration, we probe X and Y transitions. In the “edge” configuration (Figure 1d), the light was reflected from the edge of the crystal giving access to the Z-exciton state with a dipole moment oriented perpendicular to both in-plane states. As shown in Figure S1 (Supporting Information), investigated crystals were large and thick enough to easily find flat areas on the plane and edge of the crystal significantly larger than the reflected white light spot $\approx 2\text{--}4$ μm .

The results of these measurements are summarized in the Figure 2. The red and green lines in the Figure 2a correspond to the spectrum of two orthogonal polarizations of white light reflected from the plane of the investigated crystal. The two sharp resonances around ≈ 2.353 and ≈ 2.355 eV are signatures of the X and Y in-plane excitonic states^[22] (the direction of polarization were selected to probe selectively X or Y state). The high-energy side of the reflectance spectrum is affected by broad bands with energy spacing around 30–40 meV. They are probably related to the polaronic effects/phonon replicas characteristic for $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ and other soft 2DPs.^[7,46–49] To probe the Z-state with the out-of-plane dipole orientation (see the sketch in panel (a)), we measure the reflectance spectrum of the light polarized along the *c*-axis of the crystal (in the “edge” configuration) which

is shown as a blue curve. In this case, the spectrum is dominated by a single strong resonance, which we attribute to the Z-exciton state.

Interestingly, the high-energy sidebands vanish when the light is polarized perpendicular to the sample plane. We suppose this behavior results from the inherent anisotropy of 2DP, whose properties are very different in- and out-of-plane directions.^[50–52] Assuming based on previous works that the broad sideband visible for in-plane exciton states is a result of phonon-replicas^[46,47,49] we conclude that exciton-phonon coupling also exhibits strong anisotropy and vanishes for excitons with the out-of-plane dipole orientation. Further detailed analysis of the broad, high-energy part of the spectrum is beyond the scope of this work, but it certainly characterizes states with an in-plane dipole moment”. When the polarization direction is along the edge (in the “edge” configuration), probing in-plane states, the broad sidebands are recovered (as shown in Figure S3, Supporting Information see also^[49,53,54]). Unfortunately in the “edge” configuration, we cannot clearly resolve any of the in-plane states, probably due to the lower quality of the crystal edge than the surface.

To corroborate the out-of-plane orientation of the Z-state, we measured the full dependence of the reflectance spectrum versus the light polarization angle with respect to the *c*-axis of the crystal. The energy and oscillator strength of the transition can be more easily seen by taking the negative derivative $-dR/dE$ of the measured reflectance as shown in the inset of Figure 2a. The derivation of the reflectance resonance produces a peak at the energies of the transition, while the area under the peak is proportional to the oscillator strength of the transition.^[55] As shown in Figure 2b the $-dR/dE$ reaches a maximum when the light

Figure 3. a) The photoluminescence spectrum measured in the magnetic field of 6 T (gray spectrum). The small peak visible below 2.34 eV is a hallmark of the dark exciton state.^[22] The colored lines are the negative derivative of the reflectance spectra (without the magnetic field) showing the energy positions of all of the bright excitonic states. b) Dependence of the energy of the excitonic state versus the magnetic field applied in the Faraday configuration. Energies of the dark excitonic states are taken after,^[22] and lines are calculated according to the Equation 1. c) Summary of electron and hole g -factors for $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ (squares with uncertainty) and MAPbI_3 (stars) after.^[56] The intermediate values are calculated according to formula $g_{e(h)}(\theta) = \sqrt{g_{e(h)\parallel}^2 \cos^2(\theta) + g_{e(h)\perp}^2 \sin^2(\theta)}$. All measurements were done in $T = 4.2$ K.

polarization is along the direction of c -axis and the signal attributed to the Z-state vanishes when light is polarized along the crystal edge. The same conclusions can be drawn from the polarization dependence of the transition intensity summarized in the form of the polar plot in Figure 2c. The clearly visible double lobe shape, oriented along the c -axis of the crystal, is characteristic for a linearly polarized transition.

Having identified all three bright excitonic transitions, we can now elucidate the order of bright exciton states in $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$. Figure 3a shows the derivative of reflectance spectra ($-dR/dE$) measured with the use of linearly polarized light oriented along particular transitions' dipole moment. The X and Y state spectra were measured in the "plane" configuration, while for the Z state we used the "edge" configuration. As can be seen, the Z-state is located above two in-plane states (this result is consistently observed for both sets of samples as shown in SI), around 3.4 and 1.3 meV above X and Y transitions, respectively. All three bright states are situated around 15 meV above the dark state, revealed in recent magneto-PL studies (grey photoluminescence spectrum),^[22] as summarized in the scheme in Figure 3a. Presented results corroborate bright state order emerging from recent first principle calculations and some effective mass models for Lead-Iodide 2D-perovskites and nanocrystals.^[27,29,30] However, the theoretical prediction seems to overestimate the value of the Z-state splitting suggesting tens of meV splitting between in-plane and out-of-plane states.

In order to exclude the potential impact of the crystal termination at the edge on the energy of excitonic transition we also measure the reflectance spectrum from the plane of the crystal using a high numerical aperture objective ($\text{NA}=0.82$), which provided access to optical transition with the out-of-plane orientation. As it is shown in Figure S4 (Supporting Information) we observed a new feature (with respect to the case with low aperture objective

($\text{NA}=0.55$)) 1.3–1.5 meV above the highest in-plane states corroborating conclusions derived from "edge" measurements.

Knowing the energy of the Z state allows us not only to complete the picture of excitonic states but also to determine the electron and hole g -factors. Applying magnetic field in the Faraday configuration, (i.e., $\mathbf{B} \parallel \mathbf{k} \parallel \mathbf{c}$) results in the mixing of D and Z states with each other and the two in-plane states.^[32–34] The energy shift of the transitions, induced by the magnetic field gives a direct handle to the g -factors, which are described by the following formula (for two pairs of states):^[33,34]

$$E_{Y(Z)/X(D)} = \frac{1}{2} \left[(E_{Y(Z)} + E_{X(D)}) \pm \sqrt{(E_{Y(Z)} - E_{X(D)})^2 + g_{B(D)}^2 \mu_B^2 B^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

where B is the magnetic field induction, μ_B is the Bohr magneton, $g_{B(D)}$ is the bright (dark) exciton g -factor along the c -axis of the crystal being the sum (difference) of electron and hole g -factors (g -factors along the c axis of the crystal):

$$g_{B(D)} = g_{e\parallel} \pm g_{h\parallel} \quad (2)$$

While the g -factor for the bright in-plane exciton transitions was previously measured to be $g_B = 1.2 \pm 0.1$ with the use of the high magnetic field,^[6] the value of g -factor of the dark exciton in the direction parallel to the c -axis has been missing for $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$. The red-shift of the dark exciton states has been reported previously,^[22] however, it is evident from Equation 1 that an unambiguous determination of the g -factors of the D and Z states requires the knowledge of the energy difference between these states. The fitting of dark exciton red-shift (taken after^[22]) with Equation 1 is presented as a black line in panel (b) of Figure 3. Taking $E_Z - E_D = 16.9$ meV, we obtain $g_D = 2.7 \pm 0.2$.

Table 1. Summary of exciton states splitting E (with respect to dark state) and the values of the g -factors in the direction parallel (g_{\parallel}) and perpendicular (g_{\perp}) to the c -axis of the crystal.

	E (meV)	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}
X_Z	16.9	2.7 ± 0.2	$4.0 \pm 0.3^{[23]}$
X_Y	15.6	$1.2 \pm 0.1^{[6]}, 1.6^{[57]}$	$1.9 \pm 0.5^{[23]}$
X_X	13.5	$1.2 \pm 0.1^{[6]}, 1.6^{[57]}$	$1.9 \pm 0.5^{[23]}$
X_D	0	2.7 ± 0.2	$4.0 \pm 0.3^{[23]}$
e	–	$1.95 \pm 0.3, 2.05^{[57]}$	$2.9 \pm 0.6^{[23]}, 2.45^{[57]}$
h	–	$-0.75 \pm 0.3, -0.45^{[57]}$	$-1.1 \pm 0.6^{[23]}$

The dashed curves represent the evolution of the bright states in the magnetic field with previously determined parameters.^[6,22] Based on $g_D = 2.7$ and $g_B = 1.2$,^[6] we estimate the values of independent electron and hole g -factor parallel to c -axis to be $g_{e\parallel} = 1.95 \pm 0.3$ and $g_{h\parallel} = -0.75 \pm 0.3$. The determined electron $g_{e\parallel} = 1.95$ is in very good agreement with that obtained from recent Kerr rotation measurements.^[57]

It is interesting to compare the g -factors of carriers in $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ with the bulk ancestor, MAPbI_3 , as such a comparison reveals a deviation from the predictions of effective mass models for the g -factors of $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$. Panel (c) in Figure 3 shows combined results of Faraday ($\Theta = 0^\circ$) and Voigt ($\Theta = 90^\circ$) measurements for both compounds.^[23,56] Based on an effective mass model, we expect that when the bandgap increases, the electron g -factor should decrease, while the hole g -factor should increase.^[56] As can be seen in Figure 3c, these predictions are valid only for the case of g_{\parallel} for the electron. We also notice that the evolution of electron g -factors with Θ are opposite for $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ and MAPbI_4 . All those facts indicate that quantum confinement together with octahedral distortion imposed by organic spacers^[4–6] plays an important role in determining the g -factors. Therefore, conclusions derived for bulk perovskites have to be applied with particular caution in 2DP. For convenience, we summarize the exciton fine structure together with the extracted and previously reported g -factors for $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ in the Table 1.

3. Conclusion

We have provided a full description of the bright exciton fine structure in $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$. Using polarization-resolved reflectance measurements from the edge of quantum wells, we have obtained exclusive access to the Z -state with its dipole moment oriented out of the plane of the 2D crystal. We demonstrate that the Z state is energetically located above the two bright in-plane states. Our results contradict the general predictions of effective mass theory^[31,37] while corroborating the results of very recent ab-initio calculations.^[27,29] Knowing the position of the Z -state, we have for the first time, reported the values of the g -factors of the Z -state and dark excitons (along the c -axis direction). This allows us to determine the individual g -factors of electrons and holes, providing a firm benchmark for band structure models.

4. Experimental Section

Synthesis and Sample Preparation: Synthesis of two samples was performed using two different methods; i) a cooling-induced crystalliza-

tion, described in detail in [44, 45] and ii) a the slow evaporation of a solvent.^[22]

Optical Measurements: For the reflectance measurements, the samples were mounted in the cold finger He flow optical cryostat. Measurements in the “edge” configuration were done using an additional copper plate with a vertical surface (cube). All these measurements were performed at 4.2 K. For reflectance measurements, the white light was provided by a Tungsten halogen light source. For the excitation and signal collection, it used a long working distance 50 \times magnification microscope objective with numerical aperture NA=0.55. The signal was dispersed with a 500 mm long monochromator, equipped with a grating of 1200 grooves per mm, and detected using a liquid nitrogen-cooled CCD camera. Polarization optics were mounted in the excitation path of this setup.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

The authors appreciate the support of the National Science Centre Poland within programs MAESTRO (grant no. 2020/38/A/ST3/00214) and SONATA (grants no. 2020/39/D/ST3/03000 and 2021/43/D/ST3/01444). M.D. appreciates the support from the Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (grant no. BPN/BKK/2021/1/00002/U/00001) and OPUS (grant nos. 2018/31/B/ST3/02111 (N.Z. and M.R.M.) and 2017/27/B/ST3/00205 (A.B)). The Polish participation in the European Magnetic Field Laboratory (EMFL) was supported by the DIR/WK/2018/07 grant from the Ministry of Education and Science, Poland. Work by W.P. and W.A.T. at MIT was supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Basic Energy Sciences, under award number DE-SC0019345. This study had been partially supported through the EUR grant NanoX no. ANR-17-EURE-0009 in the framework of the “Programme des Investissements d’Avenir.” The access to facilities was supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through ISABEL project (no. 871106).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

2D perovskites, excitons, fine structure splitting

Received: April 13, 2023
Revised: June 21, 2023
Published online: July 23, 2023

- [1] J.-C. Blancon, A. V. Stier, H. Tsai, W. Nie, C. C. Stoumpos, B. Traore, L. Pedesseau, M. Kepenekian, F. Katsutani, G. Noe, J. Kono, S. Tretiak, S. A. Crooker, C. Katan, M. G. Kanatzidis, J. J. Crochet, J. Even, A. D. Mohite, *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, 9, 1.

- [2] D. B. Straus, C. R. Kagan, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2018**, *9*, 1434.
- [3] G. Wang, A. Chernikov, M. M. Glazov, T. F. Heinz, X. Marie, T. Amand, B. Urbaszek, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **2018**, *90*, 021001.
- [4] Y. Chen, Y. Sun, J. Peng, J. Tang, K. Zheng, Z. Liang, *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 1703487.
- [5] M. Dyksik, S. Wang, W. Paritmongkol, D. K. Maude, W. A. Tisdale, M. Baranowski, P. Plochocka, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2021**, *12*, 1638.
- [6] M. Dyksik, H. Duim, X. Zhu, Z. Yang, M. Gen, Y. Kohama, S. Adjokatse, D. K. Maude, M. A. Loi, D. A. Egger, M. Baranowski, P. Plochocka, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2020**, *5*, 3609.
- [7] A. R. Srimath Kandada, C. Silva, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2020**, *11*, 3173.
- [8] W. Tao, C. Zhang, Q. Zhou, Y. Zhao, H. Zhu, *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12*, 1.
- [9] J. Yin, H. Li, D. Cortecchia, C. Soci, J.-L. Bredas, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2017**, *2*, 417.
- [10] M. Seitz, A. J. Magdaleno, N. Alcázar-Cano, M. Meléndez, T. J. Lubbers, S. W. Walraven, S. Pakdel, E. Prada, R. Delgado-Buscalioni, F. Prins, *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, *11*, 1.
- [11] J. D. Ziegler, K.-Q. Lin, B. Meisinger, X. Zhu, M. Kober-Czerny, P. K. Nayak, C. Vona, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, C. Draxl, H. J. Snaith, J. M. Lupton, D. A. Egger, A. Chernikov, *ACS Photonics* **2022**, *9*, 3609.
- [12] M. Baranowski, K. Galkowski, A. Surrente, J. Urban, Ł. Kłopotowski, S. Mackowski, D. K. Maude, R. Ben Aich, K. Boujdaria, M. Chamarro, C. Testelin, P. Nayak, M. Dollmann, H. J. Snaith, R. Nicholas, P. Plochocka, *Nano Lett.* **2019**, *19*, 7054.
- [13] P. Odenthal, W. Talmadge, N. Gundlach, R. Wang, C. Zhang, D. Sun, Z.-G. Yu, Z. Vally Vardeny, Y. S. Li, *Nature Phys.* **2017**, *13*, 894.
- [14] M. Nestoklon, S. Goupalov, R. Dzhioev, O. Ken, V. Korenev, Y. G. Kusrayev, V. Sapega, C. de Weerd, L. Gomez, T. Gregorkiewicz, J. Lin, K. Suenaga, Y. Fujiwara, L. B. Matyushkin, I. N. Yassievich, *Physical Rev. B* **2018**, *97*, 235304.
- [15] M. A. Becker, R. Vaxenburg, G. Nedelcu, P. C. Sercel, A. Shabaev, M. J. Mehl, J. G. Michopoulos, S. G. Lambrakos, N. Bernstein, J. L. Lyons, T. Stöferle, R. F. Mahrt, M. V. Kovalenko, D. J. Norris, G. Rainò, A. L. Efros, *Nature* **2018**, *553*, 189.
- [16] C. Yin, L. Chen, N. Song, Y. Lv, F. Hu, C. Sun, W. Y. William, C. Zhang, X. Wang, Y. Zhang, M. Xiao, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2017**, *119*, 026401.
- [17] M. Fu, P. Tamarat, H. Huang, J. Even, A. L. Rogach, B. Lounis, *Nano Lett.* **2017**, *17*, 2895.
- [18] J. Ramade, L. M. Andriambariarijaona, V. Steinmetz, N. Goubet, L. Legrand, T. Barisien, F. Bernardot, C. Testelin, E. Lhuillier, A. Bramati, M. Chamarro, *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10*, 6393.
- [19] P. Tamarat, M. I. Bodnarchuk, J.-B. Trebbia, R. Erni, M. V. Kovalenko, J. Even, B. Lounis, *Nat. Mater.* **2019**, *18*, 717.
- [20] A. Liu, D. B. Almeida, L. G. Bonato, G. Nagamine, L. F. Zagonel, A. F. Nogueira, L. A. Padilha, S. Cundiff, *Sci. Adv.* **2021**, *7*, eabb3594.
- [21] T. T. H. Do, A. Granados del Aguila, D. Zhang, J. Xing, S. Liu, M. Prosnikov, W. Gao, K. Chang, P. C. Christianen, Q. Xiong, *Nano Lett.* **2020**, *20*, 5141.
- [22] K. Posmyk, N. Zawadzka, M. Dyksik, A. Surrente, D. K. Maude, T. Kazimierczuk, A. Babinski, M. R. Molas, W. Paritmongkol, M. Maczka, W. A. Tisdale, P. Plochocka, M. Baranowski, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2022**, *13*, 4463.
- [23] M. Dyksik, H. Duim, D. K. Maude, M. Baranowski, M. A. Loi, P. Plochocka, *Sci. Adv.* **2021**, *7*, eabk0904.
- [24] M. Gramlich, M. W. Swift, C. Lampe, J. L. Lyons, M. Döblinger, A. L. Efros, P. C. Sercel, A. S. Urban, *Adv. Sci.* **2022**, *9*, 2103013.
- [25] A. Liu, G. Nagamine, L. G. Bonato, D. B. Almeida, L. F. Zagonel, A. F. Nogueira, L. A. Padilha, S. T. Cundiff, *ACS Nano* **2021**, *15*, 6499.
- [26] R. Canet-Albiach, M. Krecmarova, J. B. Bailach, A. F. Gualdrón-Reyes, J. Rodríguez-Romero, S. Gorji, H. Pashaei-Adl, I. Mora-Seró, J. P. Martinez Pastor, J. F. Sánchez-Royo, G. Muñoz-Matutano, *Nano Lett.* **2022**, *22*, 7621.
- [27] C. Quarti, G. Giorgi, C. Katan, J. Even, M. Palummo, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2023**, 2202801.
- [28] P. C. Sercel, J. L. Lyons, D. Wickramaratne, R. Vaxenburg, N. Bernstein, A. L. Efros, *Nano Lett.* **2019**, *19*, 4068.
- [29] R. Ben Aich, S. Ben Radhia, K. Boujdaria, M. Chamarro, C. Testelin, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2020**, *11*, 808.
- [30] G. Biffi, Y. Cho, R. Krahne, T. C. Berkelbach, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2023**, *127*, 1891.
- [31] K. Tanaka, T. Takahashi, T. Kondo, K. Umeda, K. Ema, T. Umebayashi, K. Asai, K. Uchida, N. Miura, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **2005**, *44*, 5923.
- [32] Z. Yu, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 1.
- [33] T. Kataoka, T. Kondo, R. Ito, S. Sasaki, K. Uchida, N. Miura, *Phys. B: Condens. Matter* **1993**, *184*, 132.
- [34] A. Surrente, M. Baranowski, P. Plochocka, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2021**, *118*, 170501.
- [35] H.-h. Fang, J. Yang, S. Adjokatse, E. Tekelenburg, M. E. Kamminga, H. Duim, J. Ye, G. R. Blake, J. Even, M. A. Loi, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 1907979.
- [36] S. Wang, M. Dyksik, C. Lampe, M. Gramlich, D. K. Maude, M. Baranowski, A. S. Urban, P. Plochocka, A. Surrente, *Nano Lett.* **2022**, *22*, 7011.
- [37] K. Ema, K. Umeda, M. Toda, C. Yajima, Y. Arai, H. Kunugita, D. Wolverson, J. Davies, *Phys. Rev. B* **2006**, *73*, 241310.
- [38] M. Steger, S. M. Janke, P. C. Sercel, B. W. Larson, H. Lu, X. Qin, V. W.-z. Yu, V. Blum, J. L. Blackburn, *Nanoscale* **2022**, *14*, 752.
- [39] A. Fieramosca, L. De Marco, M. Passoni, L. Polimeno, A. Rizzo, B. L. Rosa, G. Cruciani, L. Dominici, M. De Giorgi, G. Gigli, L. C. Andreani, D. Gerace, D. Ballarini, D. Sanvitto, *Acs Photonics* **2018**, *5*, 4179.
- [40] P. Senellart, G. Solomon, A. White, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2017**, *12*, 1026.
- [41] R. M. Stevenson, R. J. Young, P. Atkinson, K. Cooper, D. A. Ritchie, A. J. Shields, *Nature* **2006**, *439*, 179.
- [42] X.-G. Zhao, G. M. Dalpian, Z. Wang, A. Zunger, *Phys. Rev. B* **2020**, *101*, 155137.
- [43] K. Momma, F. Izumi, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* **2011**, *44*, 1272.
- [44] W. Paritmongkol, N. S. Dahod, A. Stollmann, N. Mao, C. Settens, S.-L. Zheng, W. A. Tisdale, *Chem. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 5592.
- [45] W. Paritmongkol, E. R. Powers, N. S. Dahod, W. A. Tisdale, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2020**, *11*, 8565.
- [46] J. M. Urban, G. Chéhadé, M. Dyksik, M. Menahem, A. Surrente, G. Trippé-Allard, D. K. Maude, D. Garrot, O. Yaffe, E. Deleporte, P. Plochocka, M. Baranowski, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2020**, *11*, 5830.
- [47] D. B. Straus, S. Hurtado Parra, N. Iotov, J. Gebhardt, A. M. Rappe, J. E. Subotnik, J. M. Kikkawa, C. R. Kagan, *JACS* **2016**, *138*, 13798.
- [48] S. Neutzner, F. Thouin, D. Cortecchia, A. Petrozza, C. Silva, A. R. S. Kandada, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **2018**, *2*, 064605.
- [49] K. Posmyk, M. Dyksik, A. Surrente, K. Zalewska, M. Śmirtka, E. Cybula, W. Paritmongkol, W. A. Tisdale, P. Plochocka, M. Baranowski, *Nanomaterials* **2023**, *13*, 1119.
- [50] X. Hong, T. Ishihara, A. Nurmikko, *Solid State Commun.* **1992**, *84*, 657.
- [51] A. Maiti, K. Agarwal, S. Gonzalez-Munoz, O. V. Kolosov, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **2023**, *7*, 023801.
- [52] H. Tsai, W. Nie, J.-C. Blancon, C. C. Stoumpos, R. Asadpour, B. Harutyunyan, A. J. Neukirch, R. Verduzco, J. J. Crochet, S. Tretiak, L. Pedesseau, J. Even, M. A. Alam, G. Gupta, J. Lou, P. M. Ajayan, M. J. Bedzyk, M. G. Kanatzidis, A. D. Mohite, *Nature* **2016**, *536*, 312.
- [53] X. Hong, T. Ishihara, A. Nurmikko, *Phys. Rev. B* **1992**, *45*, 6961.

- [54] T. Ishihara, J. Takahashi, T. Goto, *Solid State Commun.* **1989**, 69, 933.
- [55] Z. Yang, A. Surrente, K. Galkowski, N. Bruyant, D. K. Maude, A. A. Haghighirad, H. J. Snaith, P. Plochocka, R. J. Nicholas, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2017**, 8, 1851.
- [56] E. Kirstein, D. Yakovlev, M. Glazov, E. Zhukov, D. Kudlacik, I. Kalitukha, V. Sapega, G. Dimitriev, M. Semina, M. Nestoklon, E. L. Ivchenko, N. E. Kopteva, D. N. Dirin, O. Nazarenko, M. V. Kovalenko, A. Baumann, J. Höcker, V. Dyakonov, M. Bayer, *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, 13, 3062.
- [57] E. Kirstein, E. A. Zhukov, D. R. Yakovlev, N. E. Kopteva, C. Harkort, D. Kudlacik, O. Hordiichuk, M. V. Kovalenko, M. Bayer, *Nano Lett.* **2022**, 23, 205.